

Preliminary Chemical Examination of *Aegle Marmelos* or the Indian Bel.

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Aegle marmelos or the Indian Bel (N. O. *Rutaceae*) is a large deciduous tree which grows throughout tropical India, mainly in the cultivated state. Its branches are armed with sharp straight spines, 1-2 inches in length. The bark which is nearly half an inch thick has got a soft outer substance broken up into irregular flakes. The wood is yellowish-white in colour, hard and with a strongly aromatic smell when freshly cut. The leaves are alternate and trifoliate and bright green in colour. The flowers are greenish-white, about one inch in diameter and possessing a fine sweet smell. The fruit is 4-6 inches in diameter with a smooth yellowish-grey outer rind which is hard and brittle. The inside of the ripe fruit is filled with a bright yellow, soft pulpy substance having an intense aromatic odour. The seeds which are about $\frac{1}{4}$ -inch long, closely resemble those of the orange and are embedded in the inner core of the pulp inside an outer layer of transparent and exceedingly sticky gum. The taste of the fruit is sweet with a slightly astringent tinge. The gum and the seeds are bitter.

The importance of the Bel tree from the medicinal point of view is very great indeed. Practically every part of it has been used in Indian medicines from time immemorial. There are innumerable references to it in the *Nighantas* and in the works of Charaka, Sushruta, Mohammed Hossain and more recently of Dymock, Hooker, Kirtikar, Fitzpatrick, Lanohester and others. The leaves are made into poultice and used in the treatment of ophthalmia and ulcers, and the fresh diluted juice is recommended for catarrh and feverishness. The fresh juice of the leaves is also used along with a few other ingredients in anasarca, costiveness, jaundice, catarrh, fever, delirium and a number of other ailments. A decoction of the roots and bark is sometimes used in the cure of intermittent fever, hypochondriasis, melancholia, palpitation, diarrhoea, gastric irritability and infantile liver. But the greatest medicinal value is ascribed to the fruit, both in ripe and unripe conditions. The

unripe fruit is cut up and sun dried and in this form it is sold in the bazaars. It is regarded as astringent, digestive, stomachic and specially efficacious in chronic diarrhoea and dysentery, often proving effectual after all other medicines have failed. The ripe fruit is sweet, aromatic, astringent, mild laxative and a good cure for dyspepsia and flatulence.

In view of the facts mentioned above, *Bel* stands as one of the most important medicinal plants of India, and consequently a systematic analysis was undertaken with a view to study the various chemical ingredients in the different parts of the plants and also as far as possible, to elucidate their chemical constitution. So far as the present authors have been able to ascertain, there has been no work done in this connection up to this time.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The Roots.

The roots are very stiff with a thick bark having a yellowish-white colour and a sharp bitter taste. The woody portion is light yellow when fresh, the colour soon getting bleached by exposure to light and air. The roots were cut up into small bits, dried in the air and extracted with various solvents, in 50-gram lots, in a Soxhlet apparatus. The solvent was subsequently evaporated.

Alcoholic Extract.—It is a dark brown viscous liquid (5.6%) with a bitter taste, disagreeable smell and greasy feel, and insoluble in water or cold dilute alkalis. On boiling with dilute caustic alkalis it dissolves to a brownish-yellow solution, from which acids precipitate a pasty gelatinous mass with properties practically identical with the original substance. Fehling's solution is slowly reduced on boiling, and an alcoholic solution of the substance yields a transient blue colour with ferric chloride. Concentrated sulphuric acid dissolves it with a blood red colour. The substance appears to contain a glucoside, but none could be isolated.

Chloroform Extract.—A dark brown viscous oil (6.4%) with properties similar to the above.

Petroleum Ether Extract.—It is a clear yellow oil (0.3%) with an extremely bitter taste. It gave no reaction with alkaloid reagents. Fehling's solution was rapidly reduced, but there was no colour with ferric chloride. It is easily soluble in dilute caustic alkalis from which it is precipitated unchanged by acids.

Ether Extract.—6.2 % Similar to the chloroform extract.

Benzene Extract.—6.2%. It is a clear yellow oil with a bitter taste and aromatic smell. Properties are similar to the petroleum ether extract.

Aqueous Extract.—1.7%. It is a viscous brown liquid giving a blue-black colouration with ferric chloride. (Found: Tannin, 0.7 %; reducing sugars, 0.3 %).

Ethyl Acetate Extract.—1.6%. It is a viscous brown oil having properties similar to the alcoholic extract.

Bark.

The bark was stripped from any woody portion that was left, dried, powdered and extracted with various solvents in 50-gram lots. It contains 1.05 % tannin, 1.23 % reducing sugars and 1.66% total sugars estimated as glucose.

Alcoholic Extract.—9.16%. It is a yellowish-green sticky mass smelling strongly of chlorophyll. On treatment with water it is converted into a light green powder by the removal of tannins and sugars. It could not be crystallised. It dissolves in caustic alkalis with an orange-brown colour, from which acids precipitate a yellowish-brown gelatinous mass. Fehling's solution is rapidly reduced and alcoholic ferric chloride yields a brownish-red, and alcoholic lead acetate, a dirty green precipitate. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a crimson colour. The substance appears to contain a glucoside, but none could be isolated.

Ethyl Acetate Extract.—5.6%. It is a dark green sticky mass which did not yield a solid on treatment with water. Fehling's solution slowly reduced. Alcoholic ferric chloride produces a dark red coloration and alcoholic lead acetate, a dirty green precipitate. Concentrated sulphuric acid produces a reddish-brown colour.

Chloroform Extract.—2.9%. It is a dark green sticky mass with properties similar to the above with the exception of the reaction with strong sulphuric acid in which a violet colour is developed.

Petroleum Ether Extract.—3.6%. It is a light green sticky substance, insoluble in water but soluble in caustic alkalis to a yellow solution from which acids precipitate a milky emulsion. It gave no reaction with Fehling's solution, alcoholic ferric chloride or lead acetate. Concentrated sulphuric acid produces a dark reddish-brown colour.

Ether Extract.—3.8%. It has properties similar to the above.

Benzene Extract.—1·16 %. It has properties similar to the above.

Aqueous Extract.—3·2 %. It is a sticky brown mass consisting mostly of tannins and sugars.

Leaves.

The leaves were dried, powdered and extracted with various solvents. They contain a trace of a volatile oil having the characteristic smell of the leaves and yielding a blue-violet coloration with ferric chloride. They contain 2·1% of tannin, 2·02% of total, and 1·52% of reducing sugars.

Alcoholic Extract.—9·35 %. It is a dark green solid with only a slight sticky consistency and consists mostly of chlorophyll.

Chloroform Extract.—3·72 %. Mostly chlorophyll.

Ethyl Acetate Extract.—5·0 t%. It has properties similar to the alcoholic extract.

Petroleum Ether Extract.—2·1%. It is a pale yellow-green wax, apparently contaminated with chlorophyll. It gave no reaction with Fehlings solution, alcoholic lead acetate or ferric chloride. The substance is insoluble in water or warm dilute caustic alkalis. Concentrated sulphuric acid produces a bright yellow colour. It gives most of the reactions of carotin.

Ether Extract.—6·8 %. It has properties similar to the alcoholic extract.

Benzene Extract.—2·2 %. It is practically identical with the petroleum ether extract.

Aqueous Extract.—8·8%. It is a dark brown syrup which deposits a light brown precipitate on standing. The precipitate consists of calcium and magnesium salts of organic acids and yields on ignition, 18·6% CaO and 18·7% MgO. The mother-liquor contains tannins, sugars, colouring matters together with calcium, magnesium, manganese, iron, aluminium and potassium salts of organic acids. It yields on ignition, 15·25% ash in which the proportion of iron oxide was found to be equal to 6·3%.

Fruit.

The fruit weighs from 250 to 4000 grams. The inside of the unripe fruit consists of a pale yellow pulpy mass, which on breaking up and drying in the air assumes a dark brownish-red colour,

the fully grown but unripe fruit was cut up into small pieces, dried in the sun, powdered and extracted with various solvents.

Alcoholic Extract.—10·8%. It is a dark red syrup with an intense characteristic smell and a sweetish astringent taste. It is partially soluble in water and completely in dilute caustic alkalis to a yellowish-brown solution. Fehling's solution is slowly reduced and ferric chloride yields a dirty blue coloration. The aqueous solution of the substance decolorises bromine water and aqueous potassium permanganate very readily. It contains 8·7% of reducing and 4·6% of total sugars (on the weight of the dry fruit) estimated as glucose. On ignition it yields 8·6% of ash consisting mostly of calcium, magnesium and iron compounds.

Chloroform Extract.—5·12%. It is a dark brownish-red syrup with properties similar to the alcoholic extract.

Ethyl Acetate Extract.—5·74%. This has properties similar to the above.

Ether Extract.—5·9%. It has properties similar to the above.

Petroleum Ether Extract.—3·82%. The extract was almost colourless and from this on standing, long colourless needles separated out. These were filtered off and the mother-liquor heated at 100° in a vacuum for about three hours in order to drive off all solvent. The resulting clear brownish-red oil (yield, 3·2%) on examination was found to be of the fixed type (probably derived from the seeds of the (fruit) and gave the following values on analysis:

Specific gravity at 20°	...	...	0·930
Saponification value	...	...	199·2
Acid value	...	...	26·04
Hehner value	...	...	94·4
Iodine value	...	...	114·5
Acetyl value	...	...	nil
Reichert value	...	...	3·6
Unsaponifiable matter	...	...	7·56%

The crystalline substance was recrystallised from dilute alcohol with the addition of animal charcoal in colourless silky needles melting at 103°. It has got interesting physiological and chemical properties which will be the subject of a subsequent communication. The substance has been named "Marmelosin" and is undoubtedly one of the most important active principles of the fruit.

Benzene Extract.—3.1%. It is a brownish-yellow oil from which a trace of marmelosin separates on standing. The oil is identical with that already described.

Aqueous Extract.—4.9%. It is a dark reddish-brown syrup consisting mostly of sugars.

Seeds.

The seeds of the fruit were carefully separated from the pulp by a laborious process and examined. They are exceedingly bitter in taste and contain 11.94% of oil, 17.5% of starch and 12.8% of albuminoids. The oil was extracted from the crushed seeds by petroleum ether and purified by Fuller's earth. When pure it is a light-yellow oil having the following properties.

Moisture	...	...	0.6%
Specific gravity at 20°	...	...	0.914
Saponification value	...	...	195.2
Acid value	...	...	1.8
Hehner value	...	...	91.3
Iodine value	...	...	126.1
Reichert value	...	...	2.8
Acetyl value	...	...	nil
Unsaponifiable matter	...	...	2.7%

The oil burnt with a luminous, slightly sooty, flame and on standing in contact with air, formed an elastic transparent skin on top. Taken internally in doses of 1.5 g. it acts as a very good purgative. The taste of the oil is bitter.

Further work is in progress.